

ISSN (E): 2181-4570

REPRODUCTION OF FIGURATIVE MEANS IN TRANSLATION (IN THE EXAMPLE OF UZBEK-GERMAN LANGUAGES)

Iskandarova Sevara Eraliyevna

ABSTRACT: A certain phraseological unit is sometimes neither an equivalent nor an alternative option it is possible to turn with the help of a shield. In such cases, artists are helpless they refer to the descriptive method of translation practice, with the help of this method the meanings of the units are through free-meaning words or word combinations.

KEY WORDS: phraseological, descriptive, figurative, speech, pronunciation

In these cases, the original phraseological units a word about the re-creation of the methodological tasks embodied in the structure cannot be. In these cases, the influence of the expressed opinion decreases, loses clarity and compactness. This, in turn, is the original text of fiction leads to a decrease in value.

But sometimes additional information created in the original is illustrated in the translation there is a possibility of partial restoration by road. This is, on the one hand, an artistic speech almost all meaningful linguistic means have an aesthetic-impressive profession on the other hand, due to frequent use Phraseological units have a certain degree of expressiveness it is bound to be dimmed.

Often, translators perform methodological tasks of phraseological units in the original for the purpose of re-creation, a variety of meaning enhancers typical of oral speech they refer to means that if these words are pronounced with the necessary tone only if it is done, giving imagery to the character's speech, the place of the original is known can cover the level. However, such tools are not much different from the visual method because of what they do, in many cases by means of original figurative phraseology they may not be able to replace the created methodological influence.

In short, the phraseology used in the composition of the artistic work units are used for the expression of a specific methodological task, in translation in addition to their substantive features, the author's intended method the re-creation of the goal ensures the completeness of the expression. Some from the book "Die Toten bleiben jung" (The Living Dead) by Anna Zegers if we expect phraseologisms:

"Now, comrade, put him out of your mind,

"You must beat ihn dir jetzt aus dem Kopf schlagen..."

sich etwas aus dem Kopf schlagen (müssen)

to remove from the brain (imagination, memory); like not thinking about it means.

Or another example:

"Alright, if you want, they'll help you do a favor, after all..."

"...die hilft dir hoffentlich über den Berg"

"über den Berg sein"

the color has changed, blood (red) runs down the face; dry out of water

It expresses the meaning of finding a way.

"After all, you should thank God that you are an honest person from trouble wants to save! "

"Statt froh zu sein, dass man dir aus der Patsche hilft!"

"As if the devil is to blame for every evil"

"wie alles Böse von einem Teufel kommt."

"That's it, get it out of your mind"

„schlag ihn dir doch mal georgung aus dem Kopf“.

All national specific linguistics used in the translated language adequate re-creation of meaningful and functional features of tools to the reader the national identity of the work, the behavior of the characters, their lives feel the national spirit of the people described in the work and, finally, the uniqueness of their language gives the opportunity to The main task of translation is foreign language tools as it consists in re-creating the unity of form and content of the original responsibility requires the translator to fully interpret the national character of the work of art does.

It is known that in fiction, the connection with the life of a certain people is objective this or that phenomenon and facts of the world are reflected in a figurative form will be delivered. Linguistic representation of Orazli, including its own in each language.

Phraseological combinations with specifics, unique meaning and constructional aspects will appear in the tool. This is a peculiarity in the figurative thinking of the people.

This feature is not expected in the structure of phraseologism These factors give rise to comparative and metaphorical imaginations gives rise to the nationality of phraseology.

In the phraseological reserve of each language, there are social-historical events, moral and spiritual-cultural standards, mental states,

religious imagination, national traditions and customs will be reflected.

Such phraseology belonging to a particular language group is national belongs to special language tools. They are the nationalism and uniqueness of the language determines the national color of the artistic work. Phraseological and the national character of expressions means national concepts in their content it is formed by the use of words. For example, some phraseology the component composition of the units consists of the names of the letters of the languages to which they belong will be.

Various geographical names also function as components of phraseological units can do. For example, Uzbekistan is part of Uzbek phraseological units the names of cities, villages, rivers and deserts located in the territory are found in German and components of Russian phraseological units, in most cases Gemanian and they consist of geographical names located in the regions of Russia. For example, "A dog barks at a widow from Bukhara", "He killed his mother show" as "Bukhara" and "Uchkurgan" in the composition of phraseological units there are geographical names.

The issue of translation of phraseological units with national-historical features is translation is among the least discussed problems of the theory. National This is part of the studies devoted to the translation of special linguistic tools the opinions expressed about it are insufficient. More or less this issue special researches that shed light on it are not visible today.

Phraseological equivalents or alternatives of two languages that are similar in content the variants cannot always replace each other in the translation. This is the reason the peoples to which they belong are part of some phraseological units in the presence of components that reflect concepts. Some national special phraseological expressions have their alternatives in the translated language. They are not. These methods have positive qualities as well as negative qualities. the success of the translation depends on the appropriate and skillful use of these methods depends.

Sometimes translation of works is not considered a creative process handing it over to some untalented persons who understand it as a source of income it is assumed that these translators treated the text as if they were illiterate, with many defects encountered in the practice of translating their texts fill them up, resulting in innumerable images embodied in reality, emotional-affective linguistic means do not sound like the original in translation, in short, language and stylistic means at the level

of the author's expression of original ideological and artistic content is not interpreted using However, it was chosen by the translator.

All lexical and phrasal expressions, stylistic devices, grammatical forms, words syntagmatic relations between language representatives tested, smooth, high level, literary language that does not deviate from norms and rules, improved it is necessary to have, functionally correspond to the original tools.

References:

1. Shadiev R., Shadiev N., Fayziev M. Exploring influence of cultural constructs and social network on cross-cultural learning //Innovative Technologies and Learning: First International Conference, ICITL 2018, Portoroz, Slovenia, August 27–30, 2018, Proceedings 1. – Springer International Publishing, 2018. – С. 345-350.
2. Shadiev R. et al. Exploring Affordances and Student Perceptions of MALL in Familiar Environments //Innovative Technologies and Learning: 4th International Conference, ICITL 2021, Virtual Event, November 29–December 1, 2021, Proceedings 4. – Springer International Publishing, 2021. – С. 397-412.
3. Lutfullaev M. X., Fayziev M. A., Lutfullaeva F. Pedagogical bases of use of multimedia electronic educational literature in educational process //New pedagogical and information technologies in continuing education. Samarkand. – 2003.
4. Shadiev R. et al. Comparing effects of STR versus SELT on cognitive load //2019 Twelfth International Conference on Ubi-Media Computing (Ubi-Media). – IEEE, 2019. – С. 284-287.
5. Shadiev R. et al. Impact of Speech-Enabled Language Translation Application on Perceived Learning Emotions in Lectures in English as a Medium of Instruction //Innovative Technologies and Learning: Second International Conference, ICITL 2019, Tromsø, Norway, December 2–5, 2019, Proceedings 2. – Springer International Publishing, 2019. – С. 809-814.
6. Файзиев М. А. Талабаларнинг билим ва кўникмаларини компьютер имитацион модели асосида шакллантириш методикаси («Информатика ва ахборот технологиялари» фани мисолида) //П. ф. н. дисс. Самарқанд. – 2008.
7. Lutfullaev M. H., Fayziev M. A. Basics of the Internet. – 2001.
8. Fayziev M. A. Methods of formation of knowledge and skills of students on the basis of computer simulation model (on the example of the subject" Computer

Science and Information Technology"): Dis.... Kand. ped. science //Tashkent: TDPU. – 2008.

9. Shadiev R. et al. Correction to: Familiarization Strategies to Facilitate Mobile-Assisted Language Learning in Unfamiliar Learning Environments: A Study of Strategies Development and Their Validation //Innovative Technologies and Learning: 5th International Conference, ICITL 2022, Virtual Event, August 29–31, 2022, Proceedings. – Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2022. – C. C1-C1.

10. Shadiev R. et al. Familiarization Strategies to Facilitate Mobile-Assisted Language Learning in Unfamiliar Learning Environments: A Study of Strategies Development and Their Validation //Innovative Technologies and Learning: 5th International Conference, ICITL 2022, Virtual Event, August 29–31, 2022, Proceedings. – Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2022. – C. 213-217.

11. Fayziyev Mirzaali Asfandiyorovich. (2021). TA'LIM SOHASIDA MEDIA VOSITALARIDAN FOYDALANISHNING PSIXOLOGIK-PEDAGOGIK JIHATLARI. *FAN, TA'LIM VA AMALIYATNING INTEGRASI. ILMIY-METODIK JURNALI*, 2 (5), 50–62.

12. Xamidova Diyora Jamshedovna, & Fayziyev Mirzaali Asfandiyorovich. (2023). BOSHLANG'ICH SINIF O'QUVCHILARIDA KOMMUNIKATIV TA'LIM HARAKATLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING AHAMIYATI. *Universal Science Research jurnali*, 1 (5), 726–733.

13. Toshturdiyevna K. D., Asfandiyarovich F. M. FORMATION OF THE SPIRITUAL HERITAGE OF TEMURY QUEENS IN SCHOOL GIRLS ON THE BASIS OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES //International Conference on Research Identity, Value and Ethics. – 2023. – C. 47-51.

14. Shadiev R. et al. The effects of familiarity with mobile-assisted language learning environments on creativity //2022 International Conference on Advanced Learning Technologies (ICALT). – IEEE, 2022. – C. 242-244.

